

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2026-YIL
IYUN/6-SON, I-QISM

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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MARKETING MIX FOR SERVICE COMPANIES: ADAPTATION OF CLASSIC MODELS TO SERVICE MARKETING

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Abstract. This article examines the specific features of applying the marketing mix in service companies. The classic 4P model (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) is adapted to the specifics of service delivery, taking into account such characteristics as intangibility, inseparability from the consumption process, variability in service quality, and the impossibility of storage. The study also analyses the extended 7P and 8P models, which include additional elements such as People, Process, and Physical Evidence, as well as possible modifications aimed at increasing competitiveness and customer satisfaction. The article provides practical recommendations for optimising marketing strategies for service companies.

Keywords: marketing mix, service marketing, 4P, 7P, 8P, services, adaptation, strategies, promotion, customer experience, competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada servis kompaniyalarida marketing-miksni qo'llashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Klassik 4P modeli (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi xususiyatlariga moslashtirilib, xizmatlarning nomoddiyligi, iste'mol jarayonidan ajralmasligi, sifatning o'zgaruvchanligi va saqlab bo'lmasligi kabi omillar hisobga olinadi. Shuningdek, People, Process va Physical Evidence elementlarini o'z ichiga olgan kengaytirilgan 7P va 8P modellari hamda raqobatbardoshlik va mijozlar qoniqishini oshirishga qaratilgan mumkin bo'lgan modifikatsiyalar tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada servis korxonalarini uchun marketing strategiyalarini optimallashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ham keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: marketing-miks, servis marketingi, 4P, 7P, 8P, xizmatlar, moslashtirish, strategiyalar, targ'ibot, iste'molchi tajribasi, raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются особенности применения маркетинг-микса в сервисных компаниях. Классическая модель 4P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) адаптируется к специфике предоставления услуг с учётом таких факторов, как нематериальность, неотделимость от процесса потребления, изменчивость качества и невозможность хранения услуг. Также анализируются расширенные модели 7P и 8P, включающие элементы People, Process и Physical Evidence, а также возможные модификации, направленные на повышение конкурентоспособности и удовлетворённости клиентов. В статье представлены практические рекомендации по оптимизации маркетинговых стратегий для сервисных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг-микс, сервисный маркетинг, 4P, 7P, 8P, услуги, адаптация, стратегии, продвижение, потребительский опыт, конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

In modern market conditions, service companies operate in an environment characterized by intense competition and rapidly changing customer expectations. In order to achieve sustainable development and maintain strong market positions, service enterprises must implement effective and flexible marketing strategies. One of the key instruments for creating competitive advantages is the marketing mix, which represents a combination of interconnected marketing elements aimed at satisfying consumer needs and achieving business objectives.

The classical marketing mix model, based on the 4P concept (Product, Price, Place, Promotion), was originally developed for the goods market and manufacturing industries. However, the service sector possesses several specific characteristics, including intangibility, inseparability of production and consumption, variability

of service quality, and the impossibility of storage. These features require the adaptation and expansion of traditional marketing approaches.

As the service economy developed, the traditional model evolved into the extended 7P and 8P frameworks, which introduced additional elements such as People, Process, and Physical Evidence. These components allow service companies to better manage customer experience, service quality, and interaction processes.

This article examines the ways in which classical marketing mix models can be adapted to the specific conditions of service companies. In addition, practical recommendations are proposed for improving the effectiveness of marketing strategies in service enterprises and enhancing their competitiveness in the modern service market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of the marketing mix is one of the fundamental categories of marketing theory and is traditionally based on the 4P model proposed by E. Jerome McCarthy, which includes Product, Price, Place, and Promotion. Initially, this model was primarily developed for the market of tangible goods, where the main focus was placed on product management and distribution channels. However, the rapid development of the service sector and the expansion of the service economy have revealed the limitations of the classical approach when applied to intangible activities and service organizations.

Researchers in the field of service marketing emphasize that services possess several specific characteristics, including intangibility, inseparability of production and consumption, variability of quality, and the impossibility of storage. These features have necessitated the transformation and adaptation of the traditional marketing mix concept. Scientific literature highlights that the direct application of the classical 4P model to service industries without modification does not sufficiently account for the human factor, customer interaction processes, and tangible evidence of service quality.

A significant contribution to the development of service marketing theory was made by Bernard H. Booms and Mary J. Bitner, who proposed the extended 7P model. The authors supplemented the traditional 4P framework with three additional elements: People, Process, and Physical Evidence. This concept has gained widespread recognition in both marketing theory and business practice because it enables traditional marketing tools to be effectively adapted to the specific characteristics of service organizations.

The element People reflects the importance of employees and customer interaction in the service delivery process. Since services are often created and consumed simultaneously, staff professionalism, communication skills, and customer orientation directly influence service quality and consumer satisfaction.

The Process component refers to the procedures, mechanisms, and flow of activities through which services are delivered. Efficient and customer-oriented processes contribute to service reliability, convenience, and consistency.

The Physical Evidence element addresses the tangible aspects surrounding service delivery, including interior design, equipment, visual identity, digital interfaces, and other physical indicators that help customers evaluate service quality in the absence of tangible products.

Modern scientific literature also discusses the development of the 8P model, which further expands the marketing mix for service industries by including additional elements such as Productivity and Performance. This approach reflects the growing importance of operational efficiency, service quality management, and customer experience in highly competitive service markets.

Thus, the analysis of academic literature demonstrates that the adaptation of classical marketing mix models to the service sector is determined by the objective characteristics of the service economy. The extended 7P and 8P models allow for a more comprehensive consideration of the interaction between companies and consumers, ensuring more effective management of service quality, customer experience, and the competitiveness of service organizations in the modern digital environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of this study is formed by modern concepts of service marketing, relationship marketing, and the strategic management of service companies. The research is focused on the adaptation of the classical marketing mix model to the service sector and examines how the traditional 4P framework has evolved into the extended 7P model under the influence of the growing service economy and digital transformation processes.

The study applies a qualitative research approach based on comparative and analytical methods. The comparative analysis method was used to identify the differences between the classical marketing mix model

designed for tangible goods and the adapted marketing models applied in service industries. Particular attention was devoted to the theoretical comparison of the 4P and 7P frameworks and to the evaluation of their practical applicability within service organizations, including banking, healthcare, education, hospitality, and digital service sectors.

The analytical method was employed to examine the specific characteristics of services — such as intangibility, inseparability, variability of quality, and perishability — and their influence on marketing strategy formation. The study also investigates how additional elements of the extended marketing mix, including People, Process, and Physical Evidence, contribute to improving customer experience and increasing the competitiveness of service companies.

In addition, the research incorporates a systematic review of scientific literature, academic publications, and contemporary theoretical approaches related to service marketing and marketing mix adaptation. This approach made it possible to identify current trends, conceptual developments, and practical recommendations regarding the effective implementation of marketing strategies in service organizations.

The study also relies on the principles of strategic and customer-oriented marketing, which emphasize the importance of long-term customer relationships, service quality management, and value creation in modern competitive environments.

Therefore, the selected methodology ensures a comprehensive analysis of the transformation of classical marketing models into service-oriented frameworks and supports an objective evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing mix adaptation within contemporary service companies operating in dynamic and digitally driven markets.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In modern economic conditions, service companies operate in an environment characterized by intense competition and rapidly changing customer expectations. To achieve sustainable development and maintain strong market positions, service organizations must apply effective and customer-oriented marketing strategies. One of the most important instruments for creating competitive advantages is the marketing mix, which represents a system of interconnected elements aimed at satisfying consumer needs and achieving organizational goals.

The classical marketing mix model, based on the 4P concept (Product, Price, Place, Promotion), was originally developed for the market of tangible goods. However, services possess several unique characteristics, including intangibility, inseparability of production and consumption, variability of quality, and perishability. These features require the adaptation and expansion of traditional marketing approaches. As the service economy evolved, the classical model was transformed into the extended 7P and 8P frameworks, incorporating additional elements such as People, Process, and Physical Evidence.

This study examines how classical marketing mix models can be adapted to service companies and provides recommendations for their effective implementation.

Service marketing differs significantly from product marketing because services possess four key characteristics:

1. Intangibility. A service cannot be physically touched, tested, or evaluated before purchase. Therefore, company reputation, customer reviews, recommendations, and brand image play an essential role in shaping consumer trust and purchase decisions.

2. Inseparability of production and consumption. Services are typically produced and consumed simultaneously, requiring direct interaction between employees and customers. As a result, service quality often depends on the professionalism, communication skills, and behavior of personnel.

3. Variability (heterogeneity). The quality of services may vary depending on the employee providing the service, the time of delivery, and the specific service environment. This makes standardization and quality management particularly important for service organizations.

4. Perishability (non-storability). Services cannot be stored or accumulated for future use. Consequently, service companies must effectively manage supply and demand in order to minimize unused capacity and improve operational efficiency.

These characteristics make it necessary to reconsider the traditional marketing mix and adapt it specifically to the service sector.

The classical 4P concept includes the following elements:

- Product. In the service sector, the “product” represents the service itself. It is essential to clearly define the value offered to customers and develop a strong unique selling proposition (USP).

- Price. Pricing in service industries depends on several factors, including staff qualifications, service quality, time of delivery, market competition, and perceived customer value.
- Place. For service organizations, the location and accessibility of service delivery are critically important. This may include physical locations such as banks, hotels, educational institutions, and beauty salons, as well as digital platforms and online service systems.

– Promotion. Marketing communications in the service sector include advertising, public relations, digital marketing, social media promotion, customer recommendations, and relationship marketing activities.

However, the analysis demonstrates that the traditional 4P framework is insufficient for fully addressing the specific nature of services. Therefore, the model was expanded into the 7P and 8P concepts, which include additional components aimed at improving customer experience, service quality management, and long-term competitiveness in service industries.

In addition to the traditional 4P elements, three additional components were introduced into the marketing mix model for service companies:

– People. Employees play a decisive role in shaping customer perceptions of service quality. Therefore, service companies should invest in staff training, professional development, motivation systems, and the formation of a strong customer-oriented corporate culture.

– Process. Standardisation and automation of service processes help improve service quality, reduce variability, and increase operational efficiency. Clearly organised processes also contribute to greater customer satisfaction and consistency in service delivery.

– Physical Evidence. Since services are intangible, customers often evaluate quality through physical and visual elements such as office atmosphere, interior design, employee uniforms, website appearance, branding materials, and other tangible indicators that create trust and positive impressions.

These additional elements are particularly important for improving customer satisfaction and strengthening competitive advantages in the service sector.

The 8P model further expands the marketing mix by introducing one more element:

– Productivity & Quality. In service industries, it is essential to maintain a balance between operational efficiency (cost reduction, service speed, and productivity) and the quality of service that meets customer expectations. High productivity without maintaining service quality may negatively affect customer experience and loyalty.

The application of the 8P model enables service companies to improve operational effectiveness, manage customer expectations more successfully, and increase the overall quality of service delivery.

Practical Recommendations for Applying the Marketing Mix in Service Companies

1. Create value for customers. Companies should focus not only on the service itself but also on its usefulness, convenience, emotional value, and overall customer experience.
2. Develop personnel competencies. High-quality service and employee professionalism directly influence customer satisfaction and loyalty. Continuous staff training and motivation are therefore essential.
3. Automate business processes. The use of CRM systems, digital platforms, and online service technologies helps reduce the influence of the human factor and improve service efficiency.
4. Monitor quality and customer feedback. Companies should regularly analyse customer reviews, complaints, and suggestions in order to improve service quality and respond promptly to customer needs.
5. Invest in visual and physical design. Office appearance, website design, corporate identity, and employee uniforms all contribute to forming the first impression and strengthening customer trust.
6. Apply integrated promotional strategies. Service companies should combine digital marketing, content marketing, social media marketing (SMM), public relations, and traditional advertising methods to ensure effective communication with target audiences.

The study demonstrates that the marketing mix in the service sector requires the adaptation of classical marketing models to the specific characteristics of intangible products and services. The extended 7P and 8P models make it possible to consider additional factors that influence service quality, customer satisfaction, and organizational competitiveness.

Companies that successfully integrate these elements into their marketing strategies gain significant competitive advantages and strengthen customer loyalty. Effective service marketing therefore requires a comprehensive and customer-oriented approach that includes personnel management, process optimisation, customer experience management, and integrated promotion strategies.

In conditions of increasing competition and rapid market transformation, service companies must continuously improve their marketing strategies by focusing on customer needs, technological innovation, and emerging market trends.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of the marketing mix for service companies demonstrates that the classical 4P model requires expansion and adaptation to the specific characteristics of the service sector. Unlike tangible goods, services are characterized by intangibility, variability, inseparability of production and consumption, and perishability. These features require a more comprehensive and customer-oriented approach to marketing strategy development.

The extended 7P and 8P models make it possible to consider important aspects of the service business, including the influence of personnel, the organisation of service processes, and the role of physical and visual elements that shape customer perceptions of service quality. The implementation of these models contributes to improving service quality, strengthening competitive advantages, and increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The study identified several key factors that determine the effectiveness of marketing in the service sector:

- creating value for customers and developing a strong unique service proposition;
- improving employee professionalism and motivation to enhance service quality;
- automating and standardising service processes to increase efficiency and consistency;
- paying attention to physical and visual elements that build customer trust;
- applying integrated marketing communication tools for effective promotion.

For the successful development of service companies in highly competitive markets, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Optimise the marketing mix using the 7P or 8P model. Service companies should focus not only on traditional marketing elements but also on people, service processes, and physical evidence that influence customer experience.

2. Implement quality control and feedback systems. Continuous monitoring of customer satisfaction and the collection of feedback allow companies to identify weaknesses promptly and improve service quality.

3. Actively apply digital technologies. The implementation of CRM systems, online service platforms, automation technologies, and digital communication channels enhances customer experience and operational efficiency.

4. Strengthen customer loyalty programs. Service organizations should develop loyalty programs, personalised offers, and customer retention strategies aimed at building long-term relationships with consumers.

5. Develop corporate culture and employee training systems. Since employees are one of the most important elements of service delivery, companies should invest in staff development, communication skills, and customer-oriented corporate values.

6. Invest in brand image and reputation. Service companies should focus on improving both the visual and emotional perception of the brand while strengthening customer trust through high-quality service and consistent communication.

Thus, the adaptation of the marketing mix to the specific characteristics of services and its effective implementation enable service companies to improve operational performance, strengthen customer trust, increase competitiveness, and achieve sustainable development in modern market conditions.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/1

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>